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Selection of Apple Rootstocks Suitable for Low-Yield Conditions in the Fergana Region

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Abstract: *It has been found that in the fourth year after planting, an increase in yield was observed in all rootstocks. In M-9 and MM-106 rootstocks, the yield increased by an average of 8 quintals compared to the previous year, reaching 64 and 32 quintals, respectively. In the case of strong-growing wild seedlings, an initial yield of 7.6 quintals was obtained. Our research confirmed that the process of entering the initial yield phase in semi-dwarf and dwarf rootstock apple trees begins earlier compared to those with a strong root system.*

Key words: *rootstock, adaptive, M-9, MM106, intercalary, strong-growing, yield, dwarf, semi-dwarf, sugar content, trunk circumference, cross-sectional area.*

Introduction: The scientific research conducted at the All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Fruit Crop Breeding on the creation of adaptive, high-yielding, and disease-resistant apple varieties is noteworthy. It has been established that dwarf (3-17-38, 62-396, PB-9) and semi-dwarf (3-3-72, 3-4-98) rootstocks are suitable for creating intercalary seedlings for apple varieties such as Imrus, Svejest, Bolotovskoye, Chistotel, Sinap Orlovsky, and Pamyat Isayeva [1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7]. In particular, the intercalary seedlings, which have a strong root system, have been confirmed to surpass dwarf rootstocks in terms of yield over the years [8; 9; 10].

The selected rootstock for a specific soil-climatic condition determines the level of adaptability to environmental stress factors, the dynamics of yield increase, the stability of fruit production in cultivar-rootstock combinations, and the quality of both commercial and consumer products.

Therefore, at the Fergana Scientific Experimental Station, a long-term cycle was established to evaluate local rootstocks, encompassing the entire duration from planting the seedlings to the eventual

harvest. In this process, the positive and negative aspects of each rootstock are analysed based on long-term results, allowing for the recommendation of rootstocks that are optimally suitable and highly effective for local conditions based on conclusive findings.

Research Methodology: Research is being conducted on four types of rootstocks, including M-9, MM106, intercalary, and strong-growing seedling rootstocks, in the low-yield stony-gravelly soil conditions of the Fergana Region. The studies are carried out based on the accepted methodology [1]. The mathematical analysis was performed using the method developed by B.A. Dospexov [2].

Analysis and Results: At the Fergana Scientific Experimental Station in the low-yield stony-gravelly soil conditions of the Fayzobod plot, the yield of Golden Delicious apple seedlings grafted onto four types of rootstocks—M-9, MM106, intercalary, and strong-growing seedlings—varied depending on the rootstocks in the third year. In 2022, the yield per hectare for three-year-old seedlings was 64 quintals for the M-9 rootstock, 24 quintals for MM-106, and 17.3 quintals for the intercalary rootstock. The three-year-old trees on the strong-growing rootstock had not yet entered the fruiting phase.

Table 1. Yield of apples on different rootstocks

N	Rootstock Name	Plant Density, trees/ha	Yield, hundredweight /ha			Additional Yield, hundredweight /ha		
			2022	2023	average	2022	2023	average
1	M-9	2000	56	64	60	0	0	0
2	MM-106	1000	24	32	28	-24	-40	-32
3	Intercalary	400	13,9	17,3	15,6	-42,1	-46,7	-44,4
4	Vigorous Growing	666	0	7,6	3,8	-56,0	-56,4	-56,2
HCP05: 2.7 hundredweight /ha HCP05-10%								

In 2023, that is, in the fourth year after planting, an increase in yield was observed across all rootstocks. Specifically, the yield for M-9 and MM-106 rootstocks increased by an average of 8 quintals, reaching 64 and 32 quintals, respectively, while the intercalary rootstock saw an increase of 3.4 quintals. In the case of strong-growing wild seedling rootstocks, an initial yield of 7.6 quintals was obtained.

Thus, the yield per unit area varied depending on the thickness of the seedlings suitable for each rootstock and the yield per tree. Therefore, our experiment confirmed that in both dwarf and semi-dwarf rootstock apple trees, the process of entering the initial yield phase began earlier compared to those with a strong root system.

One of the important indicators determining the quality of fruit is its size and weight. It has been found that in 2022, the heaviest fruit was observed in the MM-106 rootstock, weighing 164.2 grams (see Table 2). Nearly identical weights of 159.9 and 160.4 grams were recorded for the intercalary and M-9 rootstocks, respectively.

In 2023, although a slight decrease in fruit weight (1-2 grams) was observed across all rootstocks, it can be noted that the overall level remained comparable to that of 2022. The weight of a single fruit was 158.4 grams for the M-9 rootstock, 162.3 grams for MM-106, 156.8 grams for the intercalary rootstock, and 160.2 grams for the strong-growing rootstock that entered the fruiting phase this year.

Regarding the external appearance of the fruit, in 2022, the highest rating was given to the MM-106 rootstock apple (4.5 points). The apples on the M-9 and intercalary rootstocks were rated almost the same (4.2 and 4.0 points, respectively). In 2023, it was determined that there was no significant difference in external appearance among the rootstocks (3.9 to 4.2 points).

In 2022, the superiority in fruit taste was noted in the intercalary rootstock apple (4.5 points). The M-9 and MM-106 rootstocks were rated relatively lower (4 to 4.2 points). In 2023, the higher taste ratings were attributed to the fruits of the MM-106, intercalary, and strong-growing rootstocks.

In terms of the total sugar content of the fruit, although the highest level was observed in the intercalary rootstock apple in 2022 (14.2%), by 2023, no significant differences in total sugar content among the rootstocks were noted. Based on two years of results regarding the overall quality of the fruit, the highest rating (4.5 points) was given in the first year to the M-9 dwarf rootstock apple; however, in 2023, this superiority was not confirmed, as nearly identical results were recorded across all rootstocks.

Table 2: Apple quality on different rootstocks

№	Rootstock Name	Single Fruit Weight (g)		Fruit Appearance (score)		Fruit Taste (score)		Sugar Content (%)		Overall Fruit Quality (score)	
		2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
1	M-9	160,4	158,4	4,2	4,0	4	4,3	13,9	13,7	4,5	4,1
2	MM-106	164,2	162,3	4,5	4,2	4,2	4,4	13,5	13,5	4	4,2
3	Intercalary	159,9	156,8	4	4,1	4,5	4,5	14,2	13,8	4,2	4,2
4	Vigorous Growing	-	160,2	-	3,9	-	4,4	-	13,6	-	4,0

In conclusion, it can be stated that drawing definitive conclusions regarding quality indicators in the third year after planting, that is, in the early years of the life of various fruit trees on different rootstocks, is a challenging task. It is advisable to continue these studies to arrive at clear conclusions.

Research conducted in the low-yield stony-gravelly soil conditions of the experimental station confirmed that apple trees on dwarf and semi-dwarf rootstocks entered the fruiting phase earlier compared to seedlings with strong root systems.

The analysis of the growth and development process of the Golden Delicious variety, as well as the yield load in relation to trunk cross-sectional area, showed that these processes are directly related to the type of rootstock. Specifically, observations indicated that the one-year-old shoots exhibited more vigorous growth on semi-dwarf (MM-106) and dwarf (M-9) rootstocks.

The seasonal growth of shoots on the MM-106 and M-9 rootstocks was 56.7 and 58.4 cm, respectively, while the growth on the relatively strong intercalary and strong-growing rootstocks was 37.2 and 46.2 cm, respectively (see Table 3).

Table 3: Growth and Yield Characteristics of Apple Trees on Different Rootstocks

№	Rootstock Name	Annual Shoot Growth (cm)	Branch Diameter (m)	Trunk Circumference (cm)	Trunk Cross-Sectional Area (cm ²)	Yield per Tree (kg)	Yield per Trunk Cross-Section Area (kg/cm ²)
1	M-9	48,4	1,7	14	16,7	2,8	0,17
2	MM-106	56,7	1,8	15,3	20	3,2	0,16
3	Intercalary	37,2	1,3	13,8	16,3	2,1	0,2
4	Vigorous Growing	46,2	1,5	17,2	25,3	1,9	0,08

In terms of annual shoot growth, the semi-dwarf MM-106 rootstock showed the highest branch diameter (1.8 m), while the lowest was recorded on the intercalary rootstock (1.3 m). Regarding the trunk circumference and the corresponding cross-sectional area, the highest values were found in the strong-growing rootstocks (17.2-25.3 cm²), semi-dwarf MM-106 (15.3 cm-20 cm²), and dwarf M-9 (14 cm-16.7 cm²). In contrast, the intercalary rootstock showed relatively lower values (13.8 cm-16.3 cm²).

The analysis of yield per trunk cross-sectional area showed the superiority of the intercalary rootstock over the dwarf (M-9) and semi-dwarf (MM-106) rootstocks. Specifically, the yield per cross-sectional area was 0.20 kg/cm² for the intercalary rootstock, 0.17 kg/cm² for M-9, and 0.16 kg/cm² for MM-106. In the seedlings with strong root systems, the yield per cross-sectional area was the lowest, not exceeding 0.08 kg/cm².

Conclusion. Our research confirmed that during the early years of apple tree growth in low-fertility, rocky soil conditions, the growth, development, and early fruiting processes on M-9 and MM-106 rootstocks proceed more vigorously compared to the strong-growing and intercalary rootstocks. To draw definitive conclusions about the rootstocks, it is necessary to continue long-term research.

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